

Ferrández-Berruero, R. & Humpl, S. (2019) . What are the companies looking for when collaborating with education? In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.143-147) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641090>

What are the companies looking for when collaborating with education?

Ferrández-Berruero, Reina

Jaume I University. ferrande@uji.es

Humpl, Stefan

3s Unternehmensberatung GmbH, humpl@3s.co.at

Abstract

This paper describes a first approach to what the entities (companies) that collaborate with universities expect or demand from this collaboration. The methodology used was the semi-structured interviews and focus groups conducted with a sample of Spanish and Austrian company representative of each of the relevant categories: Ownership and size of the company, production sector, academic sector of production and if they welcomed students from a single or several programmes. The preliminary results do not show any differences in expectations between the different profiles and countries. Thus, although in any case, Corporate Social Responsibility is named as the main reason for collaboration, expectations in companies involved in external placements are related to future staff selection and others. Nevertheless, although focus groups corroborated those results, content analysis provided a new question, maybe differences come from the type of collaboration, as companies involved also in the dual system seem to be in search of learning and innovation.

Keywords

dual system; external practices; employability; university-labour market relationship.

1 Introduction

Achieving a good relationship between the university and external companies collaborating in teaching (for external practices, preparation of study plans, etc.) is a prerequisite for improving the quality of the training offer and for improving the employability of graduates (EC, 2010; 2011).

However, this relationship is not always as fluid as it should be. Most of the time because universities do not understand what the companies expect from this collaboration and forget that their partners are not NGOs. However, it is also true that other times it is companies that are not fully aware of the potential benefits and impacts that can be obtained by collaborating actively.

These benefits, as literature informs, are related to *Economic factors* (i.e. enhance company productivity, getting free staff for some time, etc.) (Basit et al., 2015; Daley et al., 2016; Healy et al., 2014; Eljido-Ten and Kloot, 2015; Ferrández-Berruero et al., 2016a; Siebert and Costley, 2013), *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)* (enhance the company social image) (Daley et al., 2016, Ferrández-Berruero et al., 2016a,b; Healy et al., 2014; Garnett, 2016; Whittington and Ferrández-Berruero, 2007), *Company modernization* (innovation and learning) (Basit et al., 2015; Felce, 2017; Ferrández-Berruero, 2016a; ; Whittington and Ferrández-Berruero, 2007; Antcliff et al., 2016; Geller et al., 2016; White, 2012 and Ions and Minton, 2012) and *Strategic planning* (search for future employees or good contacts in the university) (Daley et al., 2016; Eljido-Ten and Kloot, 2015; Felce 2017; Ferrández-Berruero et al.,

2016a; ; Healy et al., 2014; ; Whittington and Ferrández-Berruenco, 2007; Geller et al., 2016 and Hegarty et al., 2011).

This communication describes the process we have followed in the EMBI project in order to obtain a first approach to what the companies that collaborate with the university expect or demand from this collaboration.

The project concerns the following three research questions:

- 1 What do collaborating companies expect when they collaborate?
- 2 Is there any difference on expectations considering the type of company?
- 3 Are company expectations remaining stable in different contexts?

2 Methodology

The methodology used was a survey sampling using both semi-structured interviews conducted with a sample of entities selected following a quota sampling and focus groups. In both techniques, we considered the attendance of one representative of each of the categories defined as relevant to the study: Ownership and size of the company, production sector, academic sector of production and if they welcomed students from a single or several programmes.

The survey was carried out in two stages, the first one, associated to the first research question, included exploratory semi-structured interviews to 46 Spanish companies collaborating with one university in external placements. The second phase, associated to the third research question, consisted of two focus groups, one in Spain (six participants) in order to find out more about the reasons for the obtained results and a second one in Austria (four participants) to find out if those reasons remain stable in other countries.

Data analysis was mainly qualitative although Chi-Square was applied in order to make a first approach to the second research question about the differences between types of companies. As no differences were reported, the second stage, that is the focus groups, were organized focussing on the difference of contexts.

3 Results

Interviews content analysis showed that main explicit motivation was related to Corporate Social Responsibility (84%) including answers as “social obligation” or “companies must take part of social development” but, implicitly, as interviews were progressing, the search of future employees was the most evidenced (80%), and SCR changed from “social duty” to “social image” (74.6%). The third place in expectations was related to the saving resources (61.1%), as salaries, work force, etc. Table 1 shows the percentage of the main answers collected.

Table 1 Interviews main answers associated to research categories

Category	Total answers	Sub-category	N	%
Motivation	46	Corporate Social Responsibility	39	84.8
Economic factor	54	Saving	33	61.1
		Investment	16	29.6
Transformation	79	Innovation	31	39.2
		Modernization	20	25.3
		Learning	14	17.7
Corporate Social Responsibility	59	Prestige	44 (35)	74.6
		Propaganda	11	18.6
Strategy	40	Future employees	32	80.0

Note. Number of answers differ from number of companies as one company could mention more than one sub-category in its response. The actual number of companies is included in brackets when they are different.

Statistical analysis of the answers did not show any difference attending the type of companies considered. So, we could organize the focus groups in a more unified way.

Comments from participants to both Focus Groups broadly corroborated the results obtained in the interviews. Thus, although these interviews just came from one country, we could conclude that companies' expectations were the same wherever they were placed.

Nevertheless, the Focus group carried out in Austria, showed a new variable that this research had not considered so far: that is the type of collaboration. Companies in the interviews collaborated only in external placements. This was a consequence that at the Spanish context this is almost the only way of extended collaboration with higher education. But in the Austrian case, dual system is also broadly extended, and companies collaborating also in dual system seemed to be much more aware of the need of learning and modernization.

4 Discussion

It has been shown that the connection between business and education is an actual need for improving employability. But this connection cannot be built only under education requirements. Companies collaborate as they expect something in return. This research shows evidence that these expectations are mainly related to the companies' strategy for future, social image and saving resources. This agrees to some of the previous theoretical results remarked by authors as Basit et al. (2015); Daley et al. (2016); Healy et al. (2014); Eljido-Ten & Kloot (2015); Felce (2017); Ferrández-Berruenco et al., (2016a, 2016b); Garnett, (2016); Geller et al. (2016); Healy et al. (2014); Hegarty et al. (2011).

We also have shown that these results seem to be similar in different types of companies and different contexts. Nevertheless, other new perspectives dealing with collaboration appear, as it seems that different ways of collaboration could bring different expectations. Thus, the Austrian cases that used to collaborate also in a dual system, pointed out also *company Transformation* variables in their arguments.

Collaboration also defines the manifold roles of universities in society: Providing professional skills for a highly qualified workforce, taking social responsibility in training young people without restrictions and further development of disciplines and research. This raises new questions, some from technical issues: Is it possible to link expectations and types of collaboration? If so, which type of collaboration provides a wider engagement and benefit for companies? and for education? And, what about the students' dimension? How are they in-

cluded into the model? Are all the collaborations helpful in terms of learning opportunities? And others from ethical perspective: in case of conflict, which should prevail?

In any case, more research is needed, expanding the number of companies attending the same variables considered here and adding the type of collaboration. This is the only way that the connection between labour market and academy meet in a win-win relationship.

References

- Antcliff, V., Baines, S. & Gorb, E. (2016). Developing your own graduate employees: Employer perspectives on the value of a degree apprenticeship. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 6 (4), 378-383. doi:org/10.1108/HESWBL-05-2016-0032
- Basit, T. N., Eardley, A., Borup, R., Shah, H., Slack, K. & Hughes, A. (2015). Higher education institutions and work-based learning in the UK: employer engagement within a tripartite relationship. *SpringerScience+Business Media Dordrecht*, 70(1), 1003-1015. doi:org/10.1007/s10734-015-9877-7
- Daley, J., Coyle, J. & Dwyer, C., (2016). Sheffield Hallam University and Nestlé: Developing future leaders with the Chartered Manager Degree Apprenticeship – a partnership approach. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 6(4), 370-377. doi.org/10.1108/HESWBL-06-2016-0045
- Elijido-Ten, E & Kloot, L. (2015). Experiential learning in accounting work-integrated learning: a three-way partnership. *Education + Training*. 57 (2), 204-218. doi: 10.1108/ET-10-2013-0122
- EC (2010). Communication from the Commission Europe 2020. A Strategy for Smart, Sustainable and Inclusive Growth. Recuperado de <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2010:2020:FIN:EN:PDF>
- EC (2011). Supporting growth and jobs – an agenda for the modernisation of Europe’s higher education systems. Recuperado de <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2011:0567:FIN:EN:PDF>
- Felce, A. (2017). The Hub in a Pub: University of Wolverhampton Apprenticeship Hub. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*. 7(1), 70-78. doi: org/10.1108/HESWBL-05-2016-0035
- Ferrández-Berruero, R., Kekäle, T. & Sánchez-Tarazaga, L. (2016a). Universidad y empresa. Experiencias europeas de currículum integrado. Interrogantes pendientes. *Revista Española de Educación Comparada*, 27, 151-171. doi:org/10.5944/reec.27.2016.15973
- Ferrández-Berruero, R.; Kekale, T. & Devins, D. (2016b). A framework for work-based learning: basic pillars and the interactions between them. *Higher Education, skills and work-based Learning*, 6 (1), 35-54 doi.org/10.1108/HESWBL-06-2014-0026
- Garnett, J. (2016). Work-based learning: A critical challenge to the subject discipline structures and practices of higher education. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 6 (3) 305-314. doi.org/10.1108/HESWBL-04-2016-0023
- Geller, J., Zuckerman, N. & Seidel, A. (2016). Service-Learning as a Catalyst for Community Development: How Do Community Partners Benefit From Service- Learning? *Education and Urban Society*, 48(2), 151–175.
- Healy, A., Perkmann, M., Goddard, J. y Kempton, L. (2014) Measuring the impact of University Business cooperation. Case studies. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Hegarty, P.M; Kelly, H.A. Y Walsh, A. (2011). Reflection in a workplace qualification: challenges and benefits, *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 23 (8), 531-540. doi.org/10.1108/13665621111174889
- Ions, K. & Minton, A. (2012). Can work-based learning programmes help companies to be-

- come learning organisations? *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 2 (1), 22-32. doi.org/10.1108/20423891211197712
- Siebert, S. & Costley, C. (2013) *Conflicting Values in Reflection on Professional Practice*. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning* 3 (3). 156-167. doi.org/10.1108/HESWBL-07-2011-0032
- White, T. (2012) *Employer responsive provision: workforce development through work-based learning*. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning* 2(2). 6-21. doi.org/10.1108/20423891211197703
- Whittington, B. & Ferrández-Berruenco, R. (2007). *From Interaction to Integration: Developing the Relationship between Higher Education and the Labour Market*. En B. Baumgartl, F. Mizikaci, y D. Owen (eds.), *From Here to There: Mileposts of European Higher Education* (pp.179-196). Viena: Navreme (AT) y Makedonska Riznitsa (MK).

Biographical notes

Dr Ferrández-Berruenco is Associate Professor Research Methodology in Education and Educational Assessment at the Universitat Jaume I in Spain. Since 2004 she has been involved in several European projects related to increase the relationship between the labour market and the Higher education. She has collaborated also in different research projects about diversity, inclusion and multicultural education developing the role of assessment expertise. Her main research activity is related to Quality Assessment and Quality Management in Higher Education. She also performs as external evaluator for several National and International Quality Agencies.

Dr. Stefan Humpl is managing director and partner of 3s Unternehmensberatung GmbH and chairman of 3s research laboratory. His main topics in research are labour market and education system studies, and also supports the Austrian Public Employment Service through information about job and qualification trends via the AMS Skills Barometer (www.ams.at/qualifikationen), a labour market information and guidance tool that combines quantitative and qualitative information on the basis of a broad range of sources (meta-analyses). In international projects Stefan Humpl consults Cedefop (support to the Skillsnet group and to the Skills Panorama), DG EAC and DG EMPL, the UN, and the EU-Canada dialogue on Youth (with the special topic strategies against Youth Unemployment). He is experienced project manager in national and EU research and development projects in the area of education and labour market. He is consulting in curriculum design and strategic development of educational institutions (vocation education and training as well as higher education) and public bodies concerned with VET and HE, but also quality improvement in education through evaluation and feasibility studies. He was involved as expert in the development of the work-based learning toolkit (www.wbl-toolkit.eu) as well as in several activities for the European Agenda for Apprenticeships.